

Measured residues of the pesticide Fenamiphos on cucumbers pose a health risk for children

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The Brandenburg food control authorities detected elevated levels of residues of the active ingredient fenamiphos on cucumbers. Using the European Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed, it informed food administration authorities in Europe. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment has investigated whether residues amounting to 0.11 milligram per kilo of cucumber can have a detrimental effect on consumer health. Result: The measured quantity of the pesticide fenamiphos in the cucumbers tested is so high that they can pose an acute health risk for children. In contrast, they do not pose any acute health risk to adults.

For the assessment, the BfR has calculated to what extent the Acute Reference Dose (ARfD) is reached by the ingested amount. This dose defines the quantity of a pesticide which a person can ingest within one day without any appreciable health risk. In the present case, the reference dose is exceeded for children. The value is 257 %.

The active ingredient fenamiphos is neurotoxic and can impact on signal transfer in the nervous system. In Germany, no fenamiphos-containing pesticides are currently authorized.

The full version of the BfR Information in German is available on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/gemessene-rueckstaende-des-pestizids-fenamiphos-auf-gurken-sind-ein-gesundheitsrisiko-fuer-kinder.pdf>